

FINANCIAL STATEMENT ANALYSIS FOR STRATEGIC MANAGERIAL DECISIONS IN CORPORATE PRACTICE

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Abstract

The article emphasizes the importance of monitoring and regularly analyzing financial indicators to ensure sustainable growth and business stability. It examines various aspects of applying financial ratios in management practices, enabling companies to effectively manage resources, reduce risks, and make decisions aimed at enhancing competitiveness. An analysis of the financial statements of major American corporations, such as Apple, Tesla, and Amazon, demonstrates ways to develop successful growth strategies and adapt to changing market conditions.

Keywords: financial ratios, managerial decisions, liquidity, profitability, leverage, strategic planning, financial statement analysis, corporate practice.

Introduction

In highly competitive corporate world, financial statement analysis plays an important role in guiding strategic managerial decisions. Financial statements, which include the balance sheet, income statement, and cash flow statement, provide essential insights into a company's financial health. Through the detailed examination of these reports, business leaders can assess their organization's performance, identify opportunities for growth, manage risks, and make informed decisions that align with long-term corporate goals.

The ability to accurately interpret financial data is critical for maintaining operational efficiency and ensuring financial stability. As companies face increasingly complex market conditions, understanding the underlying strengths and weaknesses of their financial position becomes important. Key financial metrics, such as liquidity, profitability, leverage, and efficiency, allow managers to evaluate everything from the company's short-term solvency to its ability to generate sustainable profits and maximize shareholder value. The goal of this research is to explore the fundamental methods of financial statement analysis, and to demonstrate how these tools can be applied.

Main part. Key financial ratios for corporate analysis

Financial ratios are essential approaches in corporate analysis, providing insights into a company's financial health, performance, and stability. By examining key financial ratios, such as liquidity, profitability, leverage, and efficiency, business leaders can make informed decisions about their company's strategic direction. Each of these ratios serves a unique purpose, helping to identify areas where the company excels or may face potential risks.

Liquidity ratios measure a company's ability to meet its short-term obligations using its current assets.

These ratios are important for assessing a company's operational stability and financial flexibility in the short term.

The current ratio is calculated as current assets divided by current liabilities. It measures the company's ability to pay off short-term obligations with its current assets [1]. A higher ratio indicates better liquidity, meaning the company is more capable of covering its short-term liabilities. A current ratio of 2:1 is generally considered healthy, though this can vary by industry. The quick ratio excludes inventory from current assets and focuses on the company's most liquid assets, such as cash and receivables. It provides a more stringent measure of liquidity, showing whether a company can meet its short-term liabilities without relying on the sale of inventory.

Leverage ratios assess a company's level of debt relative to its equity or assets. These ratios help evaluate financial risk and determine how much of the company's operations are financed through debt. Debt-to-Equity ratio compares a company's total debt to its shareholders' equity and indicates the proportion of financing that comes from creditors versus investors. A high debt-to-equity ratio may suggest higher financial risk, as the company relies more on borrowing than on equity financing. The interest coverage ratio evaluates a company's ability to pay interest on its outstanding debt. A higher ratio indicates that the company can easily cover its interest payments, while a lower ratio signals potential difficulties in managing debt obligations.

Profitability ratios measure how well a company generates profit relative to its sales, assets, or equity. It provides insight into the company's operational efficiency and its ability to create value for shareholders (table 1).

Table 1.

Analysis of profitability ratios [2]

Profitability ratio	Formula	Description	Purpose
Net profit margin	Net profit / revenue	Indicates how much of each dollar in revenue results in profit after all expenses.	Provides insight into overall profitability after expenses, taxes, and interest.
Return on assets (ROA)	Net income / total assets	Reflects how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate profit.	Indicates the company's ability to generate profit using its asset base.
Return on equity (ROE)	Net income / shareholders' equity	Measures the return generated on shareholders' equity.	Useful for investors to gauge the company's efficiency in using equity capital.

Efficiency ratios assess the speed at which a company can turn its assets into sales or cash, and they highlight areas where operational improvements can be made. Inventory turnover measures how quickly a company sells its inventory within a period. A higher ratio indicates that the company is efficiently managing its inventory, reducing holding costs, and generating revenue from its products. Receivables turnover measures how efficiently a company collects its accounts receivable. A higher ratio suggests that the company is collecting payments quickly and minimizing the risk of bad debts.

Strategic decision-making based on financial statement analysis

Financial statement analysis is a powerful tool for corporate decision-making. By evaluating the company's financial health through its balance sheet, income statement, and cash flow statement, management can gain valuable insights into the organization's strengths and weaknesses. These insights are important for shaping the company's future strategies, allowing decision-makers to optimize operations, manage risks, and pursue growth opportunities [3].

The balance sheet provides a snapshot of the company's financial position at a specific moment in time, listing its assets, liabilities, and shareholders' equity. Analyzing the balance sheet allows management to assess the company's solvency and liquidity, determine its capacity to take on new debt, and evaluate the effectiveness of asset management. For instance, high levels of current assets compared to current liabilities indicate strong liquidity, which can support operational stability and investment in growth initiatives. Conversely, a high debt-to-equity ratio may suggest that the company is over-leveraged, which could pose a risk during economic downturns [4].

The income statement reflects the company's performance over a given period, showing revenue, expenses, and net income. Management can use income statement analysis to understand profitability trends and operational efficiency. Key metrics like gross profit margin, operating profit margin, and net profit margin help assess whether the company is generating sufficient revenue to cover its costs and how effectively it controls operational expenses. Declining profit margins may signal inefficiencies in cost management or a need to reassess pricing strategies.

The cash flow statement reveals how the company generates and uses cash across its operations, investments, and financing activities. Analyzing cash

flow helps management ensure that the company maintains adequate liquidity to cover day-to-day expenses, reinvest in the business, and meet debt obligations. Positive operating cash flow indicates that the company's core business activities are generating sufficient cash, while negative cash flow could suggest financial distress or the need for external financing to support growth or debt repayment.

Strategic decision-making requires a forward-looking approach, and financial analysis plays a central role in shaping these decisions. Whether the company is considering expansion, mergers and acquisitions (M&A), or investments in new business ventures, financial data provides the foundation for making informed choices that align with long-term corporate goals.

Companies aiming for geographic or operational expansion must evaluate whether their financial position can support the necessary investments. Analyzing liquidity ratios, profitability trends, and cash flow can help management determine whether they have the internal resources or need external funding for expansion. For example, a company with consistently high ROA and strong operating cash flow is more likely to succeed in scaling operations without overextending its resources.

Decisions based on M&A are among the most complex and financially sensitive strategies a company can undertake. Financial analysis is crucial in evaluating the compatibility of potential acquisition targets, determining whether the merger would create value for shareholders, and assessing the financial impact of the acquisition. Key metrics such as EBITDA (earnings before interest, taxes, depreciation, and amortization), debt levels, and future earnings potential help guide the decision on whether to proceed with an acquisition.

Entering new business lines or making significant investments in innovation, such as R&D, requires careful financial planning. Management must assess whether the company has the financial capacity to fund these initiatives while maintaining profitability. Profitability ratios, such as net profit margin and ROE, can help determine whether the company is in a position to invest in long-term projects.

The practice of financial analysis by companies

Financial statement analysis is not only theoretical but also deeply practical, guiding some of the most critical business decisions in companies. By studying how various organizations have used analysis for strategic decision-making, one can gain a better understanding

of its impact on corporate planning and long-term success.

Apple Inc. has consistently leveraged financial analysis to guide its capital allocation decisions and fuel innovation. One of Apple's key strategies has been its aggressive share buyback and dividend programs,

which were made possible through detailed cash flow analysis and strong financial performance [5]. Apple's robust cash flow from operations enabled the company to return value to shareholders while simultaneously investing in new product development. The company's current ROE is 147,15% (fig. 1).

Figure 1. The ROE as of October 2024 in Apple, Tesla and Amazon, % [6-8]

Apple demonstrates a much higher ROE than both Tesla and Amazon, indicating stronger profitability relative to shareholders' equity. Tesla and Amazon, with notably lower ROE figures, may either have a larger equity base relative to profits or are generating lower returns on their equity. This substantial difference highlights Apple's superior financial efficiency.

Amazon is another prime example of a company that has used financial statement analysis to drive its expansion strategies. From its early days, Amazon was not focused on profitability but on reinvesting cash flow into its operations and infrastructure. The company's financial analysis, particularly its cash flow statement, revealed that despite operating at a loss in its

initial years, Amazon had the ability to generate sufficient cash from its core operations to fund aggressive expansion.

Tesla's financial journey is an excellent case study of how a company can balance growth and debt management in a capital-intensive industry. Tesla has used financial statement analysis to carefully manage its debt levels while pursuing rapid expansion. By closely monitoring its debt-to-equity ratio and interest coverage ratio, Tesla ensured that it could raise capital through debt financing without over-leveraging itself. The company's current ratio is 1,91 [7]. Tesla exhibits the highest current ratio, indicating its stronger ability to meet short-term obligations compared to Apple and Amazon (fig. 2).

Figure 2. The current ratio as of October 2024 in Apple, Tesla and Amazon, % [6-8]

This represents a change of 8,52% compared to the average of 1,76 of the last 4 quarters. The chart shows that Tesla has a higher current ratio than Apple and Amazon, which may suggest greater short-term financial flexibility. However, Apple and Amazon's lower ratios could also reflect more efficient use of current assets.

World examples like Apple, Amazon, and Tesla demonstrate the profound impact that financial statement analysis can have on strategic corporate decisions. By applying financial ratios and evaluating key metrics, these companies have achieved growth, managed risks, and maintained financial stability while pursuing their

long-term goals. The use of financial data in strategic planning is not only essential for day-to-day operations but also for shaping a company's future direction and success.

Conclusion

Financial statement analysis is an indispensable tool for corporate decision-making, offering key insights into a company's financial health, performance, and risk profile. By leveraging essential financial ratios such as liquidity, profitability, leverage, and efficiency, businesses can gain a deeper understanding of their operations and make informed strategic decisions that align with their long-term objectives.

In today's dynamic business environment, it is important for companies to continuously assess their financial position to identify strengths and weaknesses, manage risks, and optimize their resources. Financial ratios provide a clear and actionable framework for evaluating the effectiveness of corporate strategies, from managing short-term liquidity to guiding long-term investment and growth decisions. Financial statement analysis not only enhances transparency but also empowers management to make strategic decisions that improve operational efficiency, foster growth, and maximize shareholder value.

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